

From Occupation Economy to Genocide Economy- *Observations from War on Gaza*

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Abstract

This paper critically examines the shifting economic frameworks underpinning Israel's policies toward Gaza, focusing on the progression from an occupation-based economy to a genocidal economic system. It analyses how systemic resource exploitation, economic dependency, and militarised profiteering sustain Israeli dominance over Palestinian land, labour, and resources within the broader context of settler-colonial capitalism. The study explores the escalation into a "genocide economy," characterised by deliberate destruction, displacement, and dehumanisation aimed at annihilating Palestinian society for political and economic gains. It elucidates the interconnectedness of occupation and genocide economies, emphasising how policies of weaponised deprivation, demographic engineering, and systemic destruction perpetuate a cycle of dependency, vulnerability, and violence.

The review highlights the role of the military-industrial complex, the international complicity that sustains these systems, and the media's role in disinformation and dehumanisation. Despite these oppressive systems, Gaza's resilient response through resistance and grassroots efforts underscores the potential for transformative change. The paper calls for a comprehensive, justice-driven approach to dismantle these intertwined economies, advocating for international accountability, Palestinian solidarity, and sustained resistance to achieve peace and justice.

Keywords: Occupation Economy, Genocide Economy, Gaza, Palestinian Resistance Struggle, Resource Exploitation, Systematic Destruction, Starvation Tactics, Impunity, Media Disinformation, Dehumanisation.

1.0 Introduction

This paper critically examines the evolving economic frameworks underpinning Israel's strategies toward Gaza, focusing on the transition from an occupation-based economy to a genocidal economic system. It contextualises the systemic characteristics of the occupation, including resource exploitation, economic dependency, and militarised

profiteering, within the broader framework of settler-colonial capitalism. Furthermore, it explores how the recent escalation into a "genocide economy" reflects deliberate policies of destruction, displacement, and dehumanisation designed to achieve political goals under the guise of military conflict. Anderton and Brauer (2016).

By analysing these interconnected systems, this review aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the economic dimensions of the ongoing conflict and their implications for Palestinian resilience, sovereignty, and human rights.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Characteristics of the Occupation Economy

The "Occupation Economy" refers to the economic system imposed by an occupying power (in this case, Israel) over a subjugated territory (Palestine, particularly Gaza and the West Bank). This system is designed to maintain control, extract resources, and create dependency while suppressing the occupied population's economic and political autonomy.

Occupation as an Economic System is not an accident but a deliberate structure that ensures the sustenance of Israeli dominance over Palestinian land, labour, and resources. Besides, it helps to ensure the Palestinian dependency on Israel for survival and the increase of profit margins for Israeli and international war-based corporations, such as arms dealers, construction firms, and settler businesses.

2.1.1 Forced Dependency on the Occupier

Control over movement (closures, checkpoints, permits) where the Palestinians in Gaza and the West Bank require Israeli-issued permits to work, travel, or import/export goods. Gaza's blockade (since 2007) restricts the flow of people and goods, crippling self-sufficiency.

The labour exploitation even before October 2023, about 200,000 Palestinians worked in Israel or settlements (mostly in construction and agriculture), often in low-wage, precarious jobs with no labour protections. Israel revokes work permits arbitrarily as collective punishment (e.g., during military operations).

2.1.2 Resource Extraction and Exploitation

The Israeli settlements (illegal under international law) seize Palestinian land and water resources. Israel controls about 85% of West Bank water, while settlers consume 6x more per capita than Palestinians. The land confiscation and settlement expansion have gone further to include

Gaza's offshore gas reserves (estimated 1.4 trillion cubic feet). Even Palestinian farmers are denied access to fertile land near the "buffer zone" in Gaza.

2.1.3 Deindustrialisation and Suppression of Local Trade

Israel systematically dismantled Palestinian industries (e.g., Gaza's textile and furniture factories) to prevent competition. The occupation even banned "dual-use" materials (e.g., cement, steel) under security pretexts, blocking reconstruction. Palestinian exports (e.g., olives, strawberries) face delays, high tariffs, and sabotage (e.g., spoilage at checkpoints). Even Gaza's fishing zone is restricted to 3-6 nautical miles (down from 20 under the Oslo Accords), crippling the fishing industry.

2.1.4 Aid Dependency and Controlled Reconstruction

Gaza relies on UNRWA and international aid for 80% of its basic needs, making it vulnerable to political pressure. Israel controls which and when aid enters (e.g., blocking solar panels, medical equipment). Even reconstruction as a profitable source for occupiers. After wars, Israeli normalised international firms win contracts to rebuild Gaza's infrastructure (e.g., sewage, electricity), reinforcing dependency.

2.1.5 Financial Strangulation

Israel collects Palestinian Authority (PA) customs and VAT taxes and withholds them during political disputes, as in the war on Gaza. The tax revenues collected by Israel on behalf of the PA amount to around \$188m each month, and account for 64 per cent of the authority's total revenue as per Al-Jazeera News Network (2024). The Palestinian banks face Israeli sanctions, limiting access to global financial systems. "Security" blacklists prevent Palestinian businesses from importing key materials.

2.1.6 Settler-Colonial Capitalism

Israeli settlers receive tax breaks, subsidised housing, and military protection. Settlement industries (e.g., Ahava cosmetics, SodaStream) exploit Palestinian resources while marketing products as "Made in Israel." Till October 2023, there were more than 30,000 Palestinians working in settlements for lower wages than Israelis, under dangerous conditions.

2.1.7 Military-Industrial Profit

Gaza is becoming a "testing ground" for weapons. Israeli arms companies (e.g., Elbit Systems) market Gaza-tested drones and surveillance tech globally. The "Iron Dome" (partly U.S.-funded) is a multi-billion-dollar industry fuelled by perpetual war.

2.2 Characteristics of the Genocide Economy

The "Genocide Economy" refers to an economic system that profits from, sustains, and accelerates the destruction of a targeted population. Unlike conventional war economies, it is not solely about territorial control or resource extraction but involves

systematic dehumanisation, mass displacement, and the deliberate dismantling of a people's means of survival.

In the context of Gaza, Israel's military campaign (2023–present) has transitioned from an "Occupation Economy" (exploitative control) to a "Genocide Economy" (annihilation for political and economic gain).

2.2.1 Weaponised Deprivation: Forced Famine & Medical Blockades

Israel bluntly follows deliberate starvation tactics, including blocking food, water, and fuel shipments (e.g., Israel restricting aid trucks at Rafah crossing). The occupiers destroyed agricultural land (bombing farms, uprooting olive trees, salinating soil). The UN-reported famine conditions (30% of Gazan children are acutely malnourished).

The Israeli Defence Forces (IDF) destroyed complete the entire health system in Gaza, which targeted the bombing of hospitals such Al-Shifa, and Al-Awda. Besides, the occupation continued to block medical supplies (e.g., anaesthesia, antibiotics). This created what one might call "dying by inches" where preventable deaths from infections, dehydration, and untreated wounds could have been avoided if medical supplies and treatment were available.

2.2.2 Mass Displacement towards Demographic Engineering

The IDF created what it calls "Safe zones" as traps, forcing Palestinians into uninhabitable areas (e.g., Muwasi "corridor") with no infrastructure. Bombing areas where displaced people flee (e.g., Rafah strikes after evacuation orders). Permanent expulsion plans are now openly advocated by Israeli officials for resettlement outside Gaza (e.g., Sinai proposals). The destruction of housing, where more than 80% of Gaza's homes are damaged or destroyed, ensures no right of return.

2.2.3 Corporate Profit from Annihilation

Israel's arms exports surge after each Gaza war (e.g., drones, AI targeting systems "battle-tested" on Palestinians), which forced the development of a dependent genocide economy where the military-industrial complex flourishes. U.S. and EU weapons manufacturers, similar as Lockheed Martin which supply bombs, jets, and artillery, are one of the benefitters of such an economy.

2.2.4 Erasure of Educational, Cultural and Quality of Socioeconomic Life Foundations

The first thing the IDF targeted was universities, libraries, archives. The occupiers started first with bombing Islamic University of Gaza, then systematic killing of professionals (doctors, journalists, academics) to cripple societal recovery. Then, the

destruction of cultural heritage (mosques, churches, archaeological sites) followed. Buheji (2024), Migdad and Buheji (2025).

2.2.5 Legal and Financial Impunity

U.S. and almost all EU block ICC/ICJ, gave impunity on actions against Israel. The sanctions on ICC prosecutors (e.g., U.S. threats over Netanyahu arrest warrant). It is estimate that the U.S. military aid to Israel surpass \$3.8 billion annually. EU and Germany continue to arms sales despite ICJ rulings.

2.2.6 Media & Psychological Warfare

The Israeli occupation followed a dehumanizing rhetoric starting from day one. Israeli officials call the Palestinians in Gaza "human animals", justifying mass killing. Western media parrots "both sides" framing, obscuring power imbalances. This was supported by censorship and disinformation that was clearly shown in social media platforms. Any pro-Palestinian voices were suppressed. Gaza hashtags were banned and shadowed. This all happened while journalists were over 100 journalists were killed in Gaza since 2023.

2.2.7 International Complicity and Silent Partners

Certain Arab states continued to trade with Israel while Gaza burned. Israel continued to export LNG to EU, replacing Russian gas, and this incentivizing Western silence. The UN paralysis that was created by U.S. vetoes of cease-fire resolutions and defunding of aid agencies, starting with UNRWA, besides the smear campaigns, all supported the international complicity.

2.3 How Both Occupation and Genocide Economies Complement Each Other

The phrase "From Occupation Economy to Genocide Economy" reflects a critical perspective on Israel's military and economic policies in Gaza, particularly during the ongoing war (as of 2023–2024). The observations and analyses of the incidents show that the IDF is intentionally trying to create a closed circuit that creates more fragility 2q2q2win Gaza resilience.

2.3.1. Occupation Economy: Exploitation and Dependence

Before the 2023 war, Gaza had been under a 16-year blockade (since 2007), with Israel controlling its borders, airspace, and maritime access. This created an "occupation economy" characterised by restricted trade and movement. Gaza's exports were heavily limited, and imports (including food, fuel, and medicine) were subject to Israeli approval. Hever et al. (2005)

Thousands of Gazans relied on work permits in Israel, making them economically vulnerable to political shifts. International aid (primarily from UNRWA) became a

lifeline, sustaining basic services while perpetuating systemic dependency. This system ensured Israeli economic and military dominance, with Gaza's economy stifled and its population trapped in cycles of poverty and unemployment (reportedly over 45% unemployment before 2023).

2.3.2. War Economy: Destruction and Reconstruction

Israel's military campaigns in Gaza (2008–2009, 2012, 2014, 2021, 2023–2024) have followed a "destruction-reconstruction" cycle. Bombing infrastructure: Each war destroys homes, hospitals, schools, and water systems, setting Gaza's development back years. Reconstruction profits: Israeli and international firms often benefit from contracts to rebuild what was destroyed (e.g., cement companies supplying materials under strict Israeli oversight). The control over aid flows by Israel regulates reconstruction materials, thus often restricting "dual-use" items (e.g., concrete, pipes) under security pretexts. This cycle entrenches Gaza's dependency while generating profits for arms manufacturers and contractors. Hasan and Buheji (2024)

2.3.3. Gaza Genocide Economy: The 2023–2025 War and Beyond

The current war has escalated into what some scholars and human rights groups call a "genocide economy"—where mass civilian destruction becomes a deliberate economic and political strategy.

The mass displacement and land appropriation have been achieved, where over 1.9 million Gazans have been displaced (85% of the population), with many unable to return due to systematic destruction. Reports of Israeli officials proposing resettlement plans, suggest the long-term demographic engineering is already in progress. The weaponised starvation is using deliberate restrictions on food, water, and fuel, leading to famine conditions (UN reports). Targeting hospitals and medical aid, created a model of clear public health catastrophe.

The economic gains of the Israeli arms defence companies such as Elbit Systems and Rafael, profiting from war-testing weapons in Gaza, are now clear. Reconstruction contracts will likely flow to Israeli and allied firms, reinforcing control.

- Gas exploration deals: Israel has moved forward with offshore gas projects near Gaza, benefiting from weakened Palestinian claims.

The US and EU are still funding Israel's military (more than \$3.8 billion/year in US aid), which helps the occupation to sustain the war economy. Corporate investments in Israeli tech and security firms (e.g., NSO Group, cyber-surveillance) thrived amid this war.

The war economy extends beyond governments to private corporations that supply weapons, surveillance tech, and infrastructure contracts tied to Israel's occupation and military campaigns. Boldorf and Okazaki (2015)

Arms manufacturers as Elbit Systems (Israel's largest weapons firm) that specialize in supplies drones, missiles, and AI-powered targeting systems battle-tested in Gaza, Lockheed Martin, Boeing, Raytheon who provide F-35 jets, bombs, and missiles to Israel via U.S. military aid and Rheinmetall (German firm) who supplies tank engines used in Gaza assaults; are all considered to be directly complacent in the creation of genocide economy in Gaza. Brauer and Anderton (2014).

Even surveillance and cyber warfare manufacturers like NSO group (Pegasus spyware), that are now an Israeli firm, facilitate to monitoring Palestinians, including activists and journalists. Companies like Cellebrite are also suspected of providing the technology to Israeli security forces for extracting data from seized Palestinian phones.

2.4 Historical Parallels: From Colonialism to Genocide

Gaza's crisis echoes past cases where economic exploitation preceded mass violence. The settler colonialism in Algeria shows how the French "scorched earth" tactics and displacement of Algerians mirror Gaza's destruction. The native Americans' U.S. expansion relied on starvation (e.g., Buffalo slaughter) and forced displacement, akin to Gaza's siege.

Genocide economy has also been experienced in Bosnia (1990s), where the Siege of Sarajevo and the Srebrenica massacre show how blockades and denial of aid precede mass killings. Rwanda (1994 genocide against the Tutsi) started with a campaign in the Early 1990s similar to what was experienced by the war in Gaza in October 2023, by dehumanisation of the Tutsi by the Hutu trip, i.e. by repeating "cockroaches" rhetoric, which parallels Israeli officials calling Palestinians "human animals." However, this genocide economy is more unique as it also uses digital warfare, where the IDF uses AI to select bombing targets, accelerating destruction. Anderton and Brauer (2016).

Western media is still highly complicit, since even though they cover some of the catastrophes of the genocide in Gaza, they also parrot Israeli framing, such as the "human shields" narrative, justifying mass casualties.

2.5 Gaza Between Economies of Resilience & Resistance vs. Economies of Occupation & Genocide

Gaza exists at the crossroads of resilience and resistance, with its people showing extraordinary strength despite ongoing hardships. While many Palestinians continue to sustain their community through grassroots efforts and unwavering resistance, the

region remains subjected to an occupation and increasingly systematic destruction. The occupation economy seeks to control and exploit Gaza's resources, enforcing dependency and disempowerment, while the evolving genocide economy aims to obliterate Palestinian presence through violence and displacement. Despite these oppressive systems, Gaza's inhabitants persist in their cultural, social, and political resistance to maintain their identity and hope for justice. This struggle underscores the stark contrast between Gaza's potential for resilience and the destructive forces of occupation and genocide. Buheji (2025)

2.6 Role of Palestinian Women During Genocide

Buheji et al. (2024) reported the important role of Palestinian women and their crucial and multifaceted role during the genocide and ongoing conflict in Gaza. They serve as protectors of their families, often taking on responsibilities such as caring for children, the sick, and the elderly amidst devastating destruction. Many women have become active in resistance movements, organising protests, documenting human rights abuses, and advocating for justice despite risks to their safety. They also provide psychosocial support to their communities, helping others cope with trauma, loss, and displacement caused by violence and destruction. Additionally, Palestinian women have contributed to humanitarian efforts, providing aid, shelter, and medical assistance in the face of collapsing infrastructure. Their resilience and bravery are vital to maintaining community cohesion and resistance, embodying strength even under extreme oppression and violence. Migdad et al. (2025a)

2.7 Structured Weakening of Trapped Economy

Hamdan et al (2025) reported the structured weakening of Gaza-trapped economy. Gaza's liquidity crisis created integral components of the broader genocide economy, both serving to entrench Palestinian dependence and facilitate ongoing destruction. The trapped economy refers to the severe restrictions on movement, trade, and access to resources imposed by the blockade, which prevent Gaza from functioning as an independent, self-sufficient economy. This confinement results in stagnant markets, high unemployment, and reliance on limited international aid, perpetuating a cycle of economic vulnerability. The liquidity crisis arises from Israel's control over Palestinian financial channels, freezing funds, withholding taxes, and restricting banking operations, thus crippling the local economy's capacity to recover and develop. Together, these conditions deepen the humanitarian crisis, weaken Palestinian resilience, and facilitate demographic engineering by destabilising society. In the context of the genocide economy, they enable policies of destruction—such as displacement and infrastructure targeting—by ensuring Gaza remains economically paralysed and unable to resist or rebuild effectively.

2.8 Consistent Destruction of Supply and Demand

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Migdad et al. (2025b) the occupation, genocide, and trapped economies in Gaza are deeply interconnected with supplies and demand, shaping the overall economic dynamics. The occupation economy restricts the supply of goods and resources into Gaza by controlling borders, imports, and access to land and water, which limits the availability of essentials like food, fuel, and medical supplies. This supply restriction leads to shortages, high prices, and increased dependency on limited external aid, reducing local demand for domestically produced goods.

The genocide economy further disrupts supplies by targeting critical infrastructure such as hospitals, water systems, and homes, creating a collapse in essential services and demand for reconstruction and medical aid. The liquidity crisis exacerbates this situation by curbing financial transactions, freezing funds, and restricting business operations, which diminishes the capacity of local markets to respond to demand.

Together, these economies distort supply and demand by creating shortages, inflating prices, and stifling local production—deepening poverty, dependence, and social disintegration. As the supplies diminish and demand increases due to necessities and reconstruction needs, the economy remains in a chronic crisis, serving as a tool of control and destruction within the larger framework of the genocide economy.

3.0 Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative analysis of the war on Gaza since its progression from an occupation economy to a genocide economy. The methodology begins with horizon scanning and trend analysis, mixing the devastating war outcome with the economic data to identify emerging patterns. Descriptive Coding for recurring concepts relative to both types of economic understanding was used to track these new trends.

The method focuses on bringing in an investigation of how the war on Gaza has been generated. The research questions how do such a progression of genocidal economy can be managed, stopped, mitigated or eliminated.

4.0 Tracking & Analysis

This paper uses descriptive coding to track and analyse the recurring concepts, themes, or ideas that appear throughout the study. Based on your literature review, the main potential descriptive codes for the recurring concepts can help organise and analyse the recurring themes in the research data, providing clarity on how the concepts interrelate across various sections in the study.

4.1 Occupation Systems: Characteristics and Examples

The occupation system in Gaza and the West Bank is a structured framework of control and exploitation engineered by Israel to maintain dominance over Palestinian land,

resources, and population. This system is not incidental but deliberately designed to consolidate military and economic control while systematically weakening Palestinian sovereignty and resilience.

Israeli-imposed restrictions exemplify the occupation's control mechanisms. Checkpoints, permits, and closures restrict the movement of Palestinians within the West Bank and Gaza. For instance, the West Bank has over 600 checkpoints and roadblocks, which fragment Palestinian communities, hinder economic activities, and restrict access to healthcare and education. Gaza Strip land, air, and sea access are tightly controlled, with the blockade since 2007 severely limiting the flow of goods and people (UN OCHA, 2021). The blockade effectively isolates Gaza economically and socially, disrupting supply chains and market access, leading to economic stagnation and dependency.

4.2 Tracking of the Dismantling of the Palestinian Economy and Increasing Its External Dependence

The occupation systematically dismantles Palestinian industries to limit economic independence. Gaza's textile, construction, and agricultural sectors face restrictions on dual-use materials like cement and steel—essential for reconstruction—arguing security concerns as a pretext. Imports are delayed or sabotaged, and exports face high tariffs or bureaucratic hurdles, crippling local enterprise (World Bank, 2020). This deindustrialisation and trade suppression create an environment of economic dependence on external aid and Israeli-controlled markets.

The occupation maintains Palestinian dependency through aid reliance, which is tightly monitored by Israeli authorities. Since Israel controls tax revenues collected for the Palestinian Authority (PA), it withholds these funds during political disputes—such as in 2019–2020, when approximately \$138 million per month was withheld (World Bank, 2020). Furthermore, Palestinian banks face restrictions and sanctions that limit their access to international financial systems, impairing economic growth and development (Palestinian Central Bank, 2021).

The occupation benefits from a thriving settler economy, with settlers receiving tax benefits, subsidised housing, and military protection—resources that fuel a capitalist enterprise rooted in land confiscation and resource extraction (Breaking the Silence, 2018). Settler-dominated industries like tourism and manufacturing profit directly from Palestinian land and labour. For instance, companies like SodaStream and Ahava utilise Palestinian resources, often marketed as “Made in Israel,” complicating consumer narratives around ethics and legality (Haaretz, 2019).

4.2 Tracking the Economic Exploitation and Dependency

Economic exploitation and dependency are major issues faced by Palestinians under occupation. Many Palestinians work in low-wage jobs in Israel or settlements, often without proper protections, which keeps them economically weak. Israel also takes control of Palestinian land and water resources, using and selling them for its benefit. Palestinian industries have been shut down or limited, making it hard for the local economy to grow. Additionally, Palestinians rely heavily on international aid and face restrictions on trade, tariffs, and finance, which prevent them from becoming self-sufficient.

4.3 Tracking the Flourishment of the Israeli Military-Industrial Complex during the War on Gaza

The military-industrial complex includes companies that produce weapons, technology, and equipment used in conflicts like those in Gaza. These companies profit from selling arms such as drones, missiles, and surveillance systems to Israel, especially during times of conflict and war. Gaza serves as a testing ground where new weapons and defense technologies are used in real combat situations, helping companies improve their products while generating profits. Surveillance technology, including cyber tools and spyware, is also developed and sold to monitor Palestinians, control movements, and suppress resistance. After destruction caused by military campaigns, reconstruction contracts are awarded to Israeli and international firms, many of which are tied to the military industry, ensuring ongoing profits. These contracts often involve rebuilding infrastructure like homes, roads, and hospitals, further linking economic gains to ongoing violence. Overall, the military-industrial complex benefits from the cycle of conflict, destruction, and reconstruction, fueling profits and technological advancements.

4.4 Tracking the Gaza's Humanitarian Crisis

Gaza faces a severe humanitarian crisis caused by a strict blockade that restricts the flow of food, water, fuel, and medical supplies, leading to widespread hunger and malnutrition. The blockade has also destroyed much of Gaza's medical infrastructure, making it difficult for hospitals and clinics to provide adequate care. Many health facilities have been bombed or deprived of essential medicines and equipment, worsening the health conditions of Gazans. Additionally, ongoing demolitions of homes and displacement of residents have left thousands without shelter, forcing families to live in temporary or unsafe conditions.

The destruction of infrastructure, including water and sewage systems, has created a public health emergency, with increased risks of waterborne diseases. Continuous violence and restrictions have prevented economic recovery and increased suffering among vulnerable populations, especially children and the elderly. Overall, Gaza's

health and living conditions have deteriorated greatly, pushing its residents into a worsening humanitarian crisis that demands urgent international attention.

4.5 Tracking the Progression of the Genocide Economy

The genocide economy involves the deliberate and systematic destruction of Gaza's infrastructure, homes, and institutions to weaken the Palestinian population physically and socially. Forced displacement is used as a tool to displace large numbers of Palestinians, often through bombings, demolitions, and creating uninhabitable areas, making it impossible for them to return. Embargoes, blockades, and starvation tactics are employed to deprive Gaza of essential supplies like food, water, and fuel, causing suffering and dependence.

Targeted attacks on hospitals, schools, and water systems aim to destroy vital services and cripple community resilience. Demographic engineering is evident in proposals to resettle Palestinians elsewhere, with plans to change the region's demographic makeup intentionally. These policies are designed not only to inflict pain and destruction but also to erase the Palestinian presence and future prospects in Gaza. Together, these tactics exemplify a calculated strategy to dismantle Palestinian society and identity, making Gaza a site of ongoing genocide.

4.6 Tracking the Legal and Political Impunity

Israel's actions in Gaza frequently violate international laws, including the Fourth Geneva Convention, which prohibits the destruction of civilian infrastructure and collective punishment. Despite these violations, there has been a persistent lack of accountability, as many perpetrators of violence or illegal settlement expansions are not prosecuted or sanctioned. International organisations like the UN have issued condemning resolutions, but enforcement remains weak due to geopolitical interests. The United States and European Union often provide political and military support to Israel, including substantial military aid and diplomatic backing in international forums.

This support helps shield Israel from international consequences and encourages continued violations of human rights. The veto power of the US in the UN Security Council has repeatedly blocked resolutions calling for sanctions or investigations into Israeli actions. Such impunity emboldens Israel to proceed with policies of occupation, settlements, and military operations without fear of legal repercussions. Overall, the lack of accountability and global support perpetuates a cycle of unchecked violence and injustice in Gaza.

4.7 Tracking Media Disinformation

The media and disinformation campaigns play a significant role in shaping public perception of the Gaza conflict. Dehumanisation rhetoric, such as referring to Palestinians as "human animals" or "cockroaches," is used to justify violence and reduce empathy for their suffering. Media framing often presents the conflict as a two-sided struggle, obscuring the power imbalance and framing Israel as primarily defensive. Censorship and restrictions on journalists and social media platforms limit the flow of independent information and suppress pro-Palestinian voices. Governments and media outlets sometimes propagate false or misleading narratives to justify military actions and control public opinion.

Psychological warfare involves spreading disinformation, fear, and paranoia through social media, propaganda, and other channels to influence both local and global audiences. This manipulation seeks to weaken morale among Palestinians and garner international support or silence dissent. Overall, these tactics distort the reality of the conflict and serve to legitimise ongoing oppression and violence.

4.8 Tracking International Role and Complicity

The international role in Gaza's crisis involves a range of silent allies who benefit from or support the ongoing occupation and conflict. Some Arab states continue to trade with Israel and engage in normalisation agreements, enabling economic benefits that weaken collective resistance. Western countries, especially the US and EU, provide significant diplomatic and military support to Israel, including billions of dollars in military aid annually, which sustains its military supremacy. This support often comes with political backing at the United Nations, where vetoes and diplomatic pressure prevent effective actions or sanctions against Israeli violations.

The global power dynamics favour Israel's strategic interests, allowing it to operate with impunity and without severe international accountability. These countries' policies often prioritise geopolitical alliances over human rights, thus enabling continued occupation and violence. The international system, through its various institutions and diplomatic channels, plays a crucial role in maintaining the status quo of oppression in Gaza. This complicity deeply influences the ongoing cycle of violence and impairs prospects for justice and peace in the region.

4.9 Tracking of Historical Parallels

The situation in Gaza shares similarities with historical cases of colonialism, where colonisers exploited land and resources while displacing indigenous populations. Like settler colonialism in places such as Algeria or the United States, Israeli policies involve land confiscation, forced displacement, and the suppression of Palestinian cultural and political identity. These patterns of occupation and resource exploitation mirror past narratives of racial superiority and legal impunity used to justify domination.

Additionally, Gaza's ongoing violence bears resemblance to instances of genocide and mass violence, such as the Holocaust, the genocide of Tutsi in Rwanda, or the Srebrenica massacre. In each case, dehumanisation, systematic destruction, and targeted violence played central roles in erasing entire communities. Like in these historical events, the use of starvation, displacement, and destructive military campaigns in Gaza reflects a calculated effort to annihilate or radically diminish the Palestinian population. The parallels highlight how systemic violence, dehumanisation, and impunity have repeatedly been used as tools of violence in colonial and genocidal histories. Recognising these patterns helps to understand the severity and urgency of resisting such policies and pursuing justice.

5.0 Discussion and Conclusion

5.1 From Exploitation to Extermination

The Genocide Economy is not just about killing people; it's about erasing anything in their future. It merges military strategy of collective punishment, economic interests through weapons sales and utilising other easy-to-liquidate assets, while also achieving political goals for the greater Israel dream that is based on the Palestinians' elimination.

The shift from "occupation economy" to "genocide economy" suggests a strategic escalation—where Gaza's economic strangulation has turned into a large-scale erasure of living conditions. Whether framed as "urbicide" (destruction of urban life), "politicide" (elimination of Palestinian self-determination), or genocide, the current war reflects a deepening crisis of international law and humanitarian morality.

This system prepares the ground for more extreme phases (e.g., mass displacement, genocide) by eroding Palestinian resilience.

5.2 Emphasising the Need for More Anti-Fragile Resistance Economy

While the "genocide economy" seems entrenched, pushback means and approaches need to grow. Palestinian Sumud (steadfastness) should go back to grassroots aid networks and solidarity economies, bypassing Israeli control. Global solidarity should also focus on boycotts further in every area to keep the Israeli's feeling the outcome of their genocide programs.

This study highlights the intricate and deeply entrenched systems of occupation and genocide that underlie Israel's policies toward Gaza and thus sets a system that needs to be carefully dismantled. The transition from an occupation economy rooted in resource exploitation and dependency to a genocidal economy marked by systematic destruction, displacement, and mass suffering underscores the severity of the ongoing crisis, but also defines the type of anti-fragility needed for the resistance economy.

The analysis reveals how the military-industrial complex financially benefits from conflict, while the humanitarian toll continues to escalate amidst blockade, targeted violence, and international complicity. Media disinformation and dehumanisation strategies serve to obscure the realities faced by Palestinians, further enabling impunity and political support for continued violations. Recognising these interconnected economic and political mechanisms is crucial for understanding the persistence of violence and resistance in Gaza.

Ultimately, addressing these systems requires a comprehensive, justice-oriented approach that challenges impunity, amplifies Palestinian voices, and advocates for international accountability. Only through such efforts can meaningful change be achieved and a pathway toward peace and justice in the region be realised.

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